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● Four new species of tribe Lepturini from continental Southeast Asia (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Lepturinae)

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Abstract: New species of the genera *Elacomia* Heller, 1916, *Mimostrangalia* Nakane & K. Ohbayashi, 1957, *Paranaspia* Matsushita & Tamanuki, 1940, and *Leptostrangalia* Nakane & K. Ohbayashi, 1959 are described from continental Southeast Asia. *Elacomia cambodgensis* sp. nov., *Mimostrangalia mondulkiriensis* sp. nov., *Paranaspia mimula* sp. nov., and *Leptostrangalia marketae* sp. nov. are described, illustrated and compared with similar species.

Keywords: longhorn beetles, Oriental Region, *Elacomia*, *Leptostrangalia*, *Mimostrangalia*, *Paranaspia*, taxonomy

● 东南亚大陆地区花天牛族（鞘翅目：天牛科：花天牛亚科）四新种记述

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摘要：本文描述了发现于东南亚大陆地区的四个天牛属的新种：*Elacomia* Heller, 1916、*Mimostrangalia* Nakane & K. Ohbayashi, 1957、*Paranaspia* Matsushita & Tamanuki, 1940 以及 *Leptostrangalia* Nakane & K. Ohbayashi, 1959。具体包括：*Elacomia cambodgensis* sp. nov., *Mimostrangalia mondulkiriensis* sp. nov., *Paranaspia mimula* sp. nov. 以及 *Leptostrangalia marketae* sp. nov.。文中提供了新种的整体图，并与近似种进行了比较鉴别。

关键词：天牛，东洋区，*Elacomia*，*Leptostrangalia*，*Mimostrangalia*，*Paranaspia*，分类

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● Introduction

The genus *Elacomia* Heller, 1916, widespread in Southeast Asia, contains sixteen known species, while significant part of them is known from the Malay and Indonesian islands. Only one species, *Elacomia michioi* (Tippmann, 1955), is known from mainland China (Fujian Province) and is the northernmost known species (Tavakilian & Chevillotte 2025). Authors who recently described new species of the genus *Elacomia* are Vives (2016) and N. Ohbayashi (2019). In this paper, a new species belonging to this genus, *Elacomia cambodgensis* **sp. nov.** from Cambodia is described and illustrated.

The genus *Mimostrangalia* Nakane & K. Ohbayashi, 1957 contains eight known species, seven of them are widespread in continental Southeast Asia, while one species, *Mimostrangalia kurosonensis* (K. Ohbayashi, 1936), is known from Japan (Tavakilian & Chevillotte 2025). In this paper, a new species belonging to this genus, *Mimostrangalia mondulkiriensis* **sp. nov.** from Cambodia is described and illustrated. This species is similar to *Mimostrangalia fluvialis* (Gressitt & Rondon, 1970), a species that is known from Laos, Thailand and Vietnam, originally classified into the genus *Strangalia* (s. str.), later transferred to the genus *Mimostrangalia* by Hayashi & Villiers (1987). In 2020, Vives described other two new species belonging to the same genus as *M. fluvialis*, however he classified them into the genus *Parastrangalis* Ganglbauer, 1889. These species are: *Parastrangalis aurata* Vives, 2020 from Binh Thuan Province of Vietnam (Vives 2020a) and *Parastrangalis sumatrana* Vives, 2020 from Indonesian Province West Sumatra (Vives 2020b). Vives' description includes information on the unclear genus classification of these species as well as information on preparation of a description of a new genus, that would eventually comprehend species *Mimostrangalia fluvialis* (Gressitt & Rondon, 1970), *Parastrangalis aurata* Vives, 2020, and *Parastrangalis sumatrana* Vives, 2020. *Mimostrangalia mondulkiriensis* **sp. nov.** is also compared with these three species in this paper.

The genus *Paranaspia* Matsushita & Tamanuki, 1940 contains thirteen known species from East Asia including Japan and China (Taiwan), and continental Southeast Asia, of which two species are reported from Laos, one species from Vietnam, and one species from Laos and Vietnam (Tavakilian & Chevillotte 2025). Authors who recently described new species of the genus *Paranaspia* are Pesarini & Sabbadini (2015) and Vives (2024). In this paper, a new species belonging to this genus, *Paranaspia mimula* **sp. nov.** from Vietnam, is described and illustrated.

The genus *Leptostrangalia* Nakane & Ohbayashi, 1959 contains thirteen known species from East Asia including Japan and China (Taiwan), and Southeast Asia. Authors who recently described new species of the genus *Leptostrangalia* are Holzschuh (2025), Huang & Vives (2019), and Ohbayashi (2019). In this paper, a new species belonging to this genus, *Leptostrangalia marketae* **sp. nov.** from south Vietnam, is described and illustrated.

The new species are compared with related species, some of them are hereby illustrated as well.

● Material and methods

Observation and photography. The habitus of specimens and genitalia photographs were taken using a Canon MP-E 65 mm f/2.8 1–5x Macro lens on bellows attached to a Canon EOS 550D camera. Each photograph was taken as several partially focused images and afterwards stacked in the Helicon Focus 8.2.18 Pro software. The photographs were modified using Adobe Photoshop CC.

Specimens examined including type materials are deposited in the following collection:

CPV collection of Petr Viktora, Kutná Hora, Czech Republic.

A slash (/) separates data in different lines on locality and determination labels. Transcription of each label is followed by abbreviation of collection in brackets.

● Taxonomy

Tribe Lepturini Latreille, 1802

Genus *Elacomia* Heller, 1916

Type species. *Elacomia collaris* Heller, 1916.

Elacomia cambodgensis sp. nov.

<https://zoobank.org/1B087003-82E1-4B92-B0B4-F77307A2DE8C>

Figs. 1–2

Type locality. Cambodia, Mondulkiri Province, 25 km SE of Sen Monorom, 12°21.23093' N, 107°17.59453' E.

Type material. Holotype (♂): 'E Cambodia / 25 km SE of Sen Monorom / N 12°21.23093', E 107°17.59453' / 840 m, 13. V. 2019 / P. Viktora lgt.', (CPV); Paratype: (1 ♀): same data as holotype, (CPV).

The types are provided with a printed red label: 'Elacomia cambodgensis sp. nov. / HOLOTYPUS [respectively PARATYPUS] / P. Viktora det., 2025'.

Description. Habitus of male holotype as in Fig. 1a. Body largely black, elongate, narrow, punctate, with setation. Body length from head to elytral apex 9.05 mm, widest at humeral part of elytra (2.23 mm), 4.05 times as long as wide.

Head black, distinct, widest across eyes, as wide as pronotum at base, strongly strangled near base, largely with irregular, relatively coarse granulation, glossy, anterior and basal part with irregular, shallower punctation. Disc and frons with narrow longitudinal furrow. Head partly with indistinct, sparse pale setation (disc with long, erect setae). Head significantly prolonged anteriorly. Space between antennal insertions very narrow, antennal insertions elevated on inner side. Eyes large, convex, blackish, small-faceted, only indistinctly emarginate on inner anterior side. Clypeus and labrum glossy, ochre yellow/pale brown, partly with yellowish setae. Mandibles from brown to black, glossy, wrinkled, with pale setation in margins.

Maxillary palpi ochre yellow, semi-glossy, widened apically, with micropunctuation, covered by sparse, short, yellowish setation. Last palpomere longest and largest, cylindrical, narrowed apically with cut apex.

Antennae with 11 antennomeres, narrow, elongate, filiform, antennomeres slightly widened apically (antennomere 11 slightly curved, narrowed apically into tip). Antennae long, distinctly exceeding apical margin of elytra (Fig. 1a). Antennomeres 1–8 reddish-brown (antennomeres 1–3 partly with darker margins), antennomeres 9–10 pale yellowish, antennomere 11 brown with pale yellowish base. Antennomeres 1–5 glossy, antennomeres 6–11 matte. Antennomeres covered by setation of shades of more colours (predominantly goldenish), setation longest on scape, short and denser on antennomeres 6–11. Antennae with irregular, shallow punctation/micropunctuation (larger punctures in scape). Antennomeres with rounded apex, without spines, some antennomeres slightly curved. Antennomere 2 shortest, antennomere 5 longest. Ratios of relative lengths of antennomeres 1–11 equal to: 0.64 : 0.17 : 1.00 : 0.88 : 1.21 : 1.12 : 1.13 : 1.03 : 1.01 : 0.89 : 1.19.

Pronotum elongate, black, glossy, distinctly convex, narrower than elytra at humeri, strongly strangled near anterior margin, slightly strangled near basal margin, widest at base, narrowest at strangulation near anterior margin, lateral margins slightly undulate, anterior margin almost straight, base undulate (shape of pronotum as in Fig. 1a). Pronotum 1.09 times as long as wide at base (widest point of pronotum) and 1.64 times as long as wide at anterior margin. Pronotal disc smooth, glossy, with very sparse, irregular punctation (with smaller-sized, dense, irregular punctation near anterior margin and base), with sparse whitish/silvery setation. Basal angles and anterior margin of pronotum with dense whitish/silvery setation (Fig. 1a).

Scutellum black, narrow, triangular, with small-sized punctation, semi-glossy, with long, recumbent, silvery setation.

FIGURE 1. *Elacomia cambodgensis* sp. nov.: **a** male holotype **b** male genitalia.

FIGURE 2. *Elacomia cambodgensis* sp. nov.: female paratype.

FIGURE 3. *Mimostrangalia mondulkiriensis* sp. nov.: **a** male holotype **b** male genitalia.

FIGURE 4. *Mimostrangalia mondulkiriensis* sp. nov.: female paratype.

FIGURE 5. *Mimostrangalia fluvialis* (Gressitt & Rondon, 1970): female from Thailand, Mae Hong Son Province, (CPV).

Elytra elongate, narrow, slightly narrowing apically, 5.82 mm long and 2.23 mm wide (2.60 times as long as wide), black with pale yellowish spots/stripes, glossy. Elytral disc relatively flat, microwrinkled, with sparse, shallow, large-sized punctation, covered by long, sparse, regular setation with lustre, apical margin with denser setation. Elytral apex rounded at lateral angles, sutural angles acute with short spines (Fig. 1a).

Pygidium blackish with paler (brown) apical part, glossy, microwrinkled, with dense, irregular, shallow punctation, covered by long, recumbent, yellowish setation. Apical angles distinctly rounded.

Legs long and narrow, largely blackish (profemora pale reddish-brown with narrowly darker margins), glossy, microwrinkled, with shallow, irregular micropunctation, covered by setation of more color shades (predominant goldenish). Setation sparser in femora, densest in apical parts of tibiae. Femora narrowly club-shaped, tibiae widened apically, slightly curved. Metatibiae and metafemora distinctly longer than pro- and mesotibiae and pro- and mesofemora. Tibial spurs pale reddish-brown, narrow, sharp, slightly curved. Tarsi long and narrow, blackish brown, microwrinkled, with irregular punctation, covered by long, dark and paler (goldenish) setation. Metatarsi longest. Metatarsomere 1 1.45 times longer than metatarsomeres 2 and 3 combined.

Ventral side of body black, glossy, smooth, partly with shallow small-sized punctation, partly covered by very long, recumbent, silvery setation (large spots on mesepisternum, metepisternum, metasternum and ventrites). Elytral epipleura narrow, black, glossy, with very sparse pale setation.

Genitalia as in Fig. 1b.

Female. Habitus of female paratype as in Fig. 2. Body length from head to elytral apex 9.0 mm. Colour of female similar to male. Female without distinct differences, body less elongate, tarsi shorter than in male (Figs. 1a and 2).

Differential diagnosis. The most similar species is *Elacomia michioi* (Tippmann, 1955).

Elacomia cambodgensis sp. nov. (based on comparison of males) differs from the similar species *E. michioi* by overall significantly smaller size, distinctly narrower body, narrower pronotum of different shape, narrower elytra with different pattern of pale yellowish spots/stripes on elytra (spots/stripes pale reddish-brown in *E. michioi*), narrower antennae, pale reddish-brown antennomeres 1–8 (blackish in *E. michioi*), and by different shape of abdominal segment VIII and tegmen.

Etymology. Toponymic, named after place of discovery.

Distribution. Cambodia (Mondulkiri).

Genus *Mimostrangalia* Nakane & Ohbayashi, 1957

Type species. *Strangalia kurosonensis* Ohbayashi, 1936.

Mimostrangalia mondulkiriensis sp. nov.

<https://zoobank.org/1E661288-D0AF-4209-AA5C-42C9991FDE6D>

Figs. 3–4

Type locality. Cambodia, Mondulkiri Province, S of Sen Monorom, 12°20'43'' N, 107°18'48'' E.

Type material. Holotype (♂): 'E Cambodia, Mondulkiri prov., / S of Sen Monorom, 12°20'43.000''N, / 107°18'48.000''E, 850 m, / 17. IV. – 1. V. 2025, P. Viktora lgt.', (CPV); Paratype: (1 ♀): same data as holotype, (CPV).

The types are provided with a printed red label: '*Mimostrangalia mondulkiriensis* sp. nov. / HOLOTYPUS [respectively PARATYPUS] / P. Viktora det., 2025'.

Description. Habitus of male holotype as in Fig. 3a. Body largely black, elongate, narrow, almost parallel, punctate, with pubescence. Last two visible ventrites are not covered by elytra. Body length from head to elytral apex 10.70 mm, widest at humeral part of elytra (2.27 mm), 4.71 times as long as wide.

Head black, semi-glossy widest across eyes, wider than pronotum, slightly narrower than elytra across humeri, strongly strangled near base, with irregular, dense, small-sized granulation, partly microwrinkled with small-sized, shallow punctation in anterior part. Head partly covered by goldenish pubescence, partly with very long, erect, pale setae (mainly at anterior part). Head prolonged anteriorly. Space between antennal insertions very narrow, antennal insertions elevated into thorns on inner side. Eyes distinct, large, convex, goldenish, small-faceted, emarginate in middle of inner side. Clypeus and labrum glossy, from brown to blackish brown, partly with yellowish setae. Mandibles from brown to black, glossy, with pale setation in margins.

Maxillary palpi brown, semi-glossy. Palpomeres widened apically (last palpomere grain-shaped with narrowed, cut apex), microwrinkled, covered by indistinct, sparse, short, yellowish setation.

Antennae with 11 antennomeres, antennomeres 1–5 narrow, antennomeres 6–11 distinctly wider. Antennomeres widened apically (antennomere 11 slightly narrowed apically into tip). Antennae long, not reaching apical margin of elytra (Fig. 3a). Antennomeres 1–2 and 6–7 dark, blackish, antennomeres 3–5 with yellowish basal half and dark apical half, antennomeres 8–11 ochre yellow. Antennomeres 1–5 glossy, antennomeres 6–11 matte. Antennomeres with dense, small-sized punctation, covered by short, pale yellowish and darker pubescence with lustre (sparser in antennomeres 1–5). Antennomeres 3–5 with long setation on inner side. Antennomeres without spines, antennomeres 6–11 distinctly widened and serrate on outer side. Antennomere 2 shortest, antennomere 5 longest. Ratios of relative lengths of antennomeres 1–11 equal to: 0.57 : 0.14 : 1.00 : 0.86 : 1.06 : 0.88 : 0.81 : 0.71 : 0.64 : 0.62 : 0.83.

Pronotum elongate, black, semi-glossy, convex, narrower than elytra at humeri, strangled near anterior margin, slightly strangled near basal margin, widest at base, narrowest at anterior margin, lateral margins slightly undulate, anterior margin almost straight, base undulate (shape of pronotum as in Fig. 3a). Pronotum 1.15 times as long as wide at base (widest point of pronotum) and 2.20 times as long as wide at anterior margin. Pronotal disc completely with very dense, small-sized granulate punctation, covered by sparse, dark pubescence with lustre (in dark places) and goldenish, long pubescence (longest and densest in basal angles and anterior margin of pronotum), basal part with a few long, erect, colourless setae.

Scutellum black, shield-shaped, with small-sized punctation, semi-glossy, covered by recumbent, goldenish pubescence.

Elytra elongate, narrow, narrowing apically, 6.78 mm long and 2.27 mm wide (2.99 times as long as wide), black with yellow and ochre yellow spots/stripes, glossy (Fig. 3a). Elytra not covering last two visible ventrites. Elytral disc relatively flat, microwrinkled, with distinct, relatively large-sized punctation, covered by sparse goldenish and darker setation with lustre, apical margin with denser goldenish setation. Elytral apex cut, sutural and lateral angles acute with short, indistinct spines.

Pygidium black, glossy, distinctly shaped, microwrinkled, partly with long goldenish pubescence (Fig. 3b).

Legs long and narrow, largely black (profemora partly ochre yellow on ventral side), glossy, microwrinkled, with shallow, irregular, large-sized punctation, covered by goldenish setation (setation longest and densest in apical parts of pro- and mesotibiae). Femora narrowly club-shaped, tibiae widened apically. Metatibiae and metafemora distinctly longer than pro- and mesotibiae and pro- and mesofemora. Metatibiae slightly curved. Tibial spurs pale reddish-brown, narrow, sharp. Tarsi long and narrow, blackish brown, microwrinkled, with small-sized punctation/granulation, covered by long, brownish setation. Claws long. Metatarsomere 1 1.50 times longer than metatarsomeres 2 and 3 combined.

Ventral side of body largely black, glossy, microwrinkled, with irregular, very dense in places, small-sized punctation, largely covered by dense, recumbent, goldenish pubescence. Ventrites covered by dense goldenish pubescence except almost smooth apical quarters. Elytral epipleura very narrow, black, glossy, microwrinkled, without visible setation.

Genitalia as in Fig. 3b.

Female. Habitus of female paratype as in Fig. 4. Body length from head to elytral apex 11.80 mm. Colour of pronotum and elytra similar to male. Last visible ventrites are covered by elytra (unlike in male), antennae almost completely ochre yellow except antennomeres 3–4 with narrowly darker apex (antennomeres 1–2 and 6–7 blackish in male), profemora largely ochre yellow (profemora black, only partly ochre yellow on ventral side in male), protarsi narrower than in male (Figs. 3a and 4).

Differential diagnosis. The most similar species are *Mimostrangalia fluvialis* (Gressitt & Rondon, 1970) (Fig. 5), *Parastrangalis aurata* Vives, 2020 (Fig. 6), and *Parastrangalis sumatrana* Vives, 2020.

Note. Regarding genus classification see "Introduction".

Mimostrangalia mondulkiriensis **sp. nov.** (based on comparison of males) differs from the similar species *M. fluvialis* by narrower pronotum, by distinctly narrower and more parallel elytra of different shape with less pronounced humeri, and by distinctly different pattern of dark and pale spots/stripes on elytra. *Mimostrangalia mondulkiriensis* **sp. nov.** (based on comparison of females) differs from the similar species *M. fluvialis* by antennomeres 3–4 with narrowly darker apex (antennae completely unicolored in *M. fluvialis*), antennomeres 6–11 distinctly shorter and wider, antennomeres 6–10 more serrate on outer side of apex, and by distinctly different pattern of dark and pale spots/stripes on elytra (Figs. 4 and 5).

Mimostrangalia mondulkiriensis **sp. nov.** (based on comparison of males) differs from the similar species *Parastrangalis aurata* and *Parastrangalis sumatrana* by darker profemora, different colour of antennomeres 6–7 (blackish in *M. mondulkiriensis* **sp. nov.**, while pale reddish-brown with darker margins in *Parastrangalis aurata* and unicolored, pale reddish-brown in *Parastrangalis sumatrana*), and by distinctly different pattern of dark and pale spots/stripes on elytra. *Mimostrangalia mondulkiriensis* **sp. nov.** (based on comparison of females) differs from the similar species *Parastrangalis aurata* by narrower pronotum, black mesofemora (pale reddish-brown in *Parastrangalis aurata*), antennomeres 3–4 with narrowly darker apex (antennae completely unicolored in *Parastrangalis aurata*), and by distinctly different pattern of dark and pale spots/stripes on elytra (Figs. 4 and 6).

Etymology. Named after the type locality, Mondulkiri Province.

Distribution. Cambodia (Mondulkiri).

Mimostrangalia fluvialis (Gressitt & Rondon, 1970)

Fig. 5

Additional material. (1 ♀): 'Thailand NW / Mae Hong Son prov. / Soppong vill. env. / 29.4. - 17.5. 2007 / P. Viktora lgt.', (CPV). **New province record.**

Distribution. Laos (Bolikhamsai), Thailand (Chiang Mai, Mae Hong Son), Vietnam (Ha Giang, Vinh Phuc).

Parastrangalis aurata Vives, 2020

Fig. 6

Additional material. (2 ♀♀): 'Dong Tien / Binh Thuan / Vietnam V. 2018', (CPV).

Distribution. Vietnam (Binh Thuan).

Genus *Paranaspia* Matsushita & Tamanuki, 1940

Type species. *Leptura anaspidoidea* Bates, 1873.

FIGURE 6. *Parastrangalis aurata* Vives, 2020: female from Vietnam, Binh Thuan Province, (CPV).

FIGURE 7. *Paranaspia mimula* **sp. nov.**: female holotype.

FIGURE 8. *Paranaspia frainii* (Fairmaire, 1897): male from Nepal, Kathmandu, (CPV).

FIGURE 9. *Paranaspia reductipennis* (Pic, 1928): male from Laos, Houaphanh Province, (CPV).

FIGURE 10. *Leptostrangalia marketae* **sp. nov.**: a male holotype b male genitalia.

***Paranaspia mimula* sp. nov.**

<https://zoobank.org/E4E5EB4D-EEC7-4BB4-8697-79F84C759B7F>

Fig. 7

Type locality. Vietnam, Kon Tum Province, Dak Ung.

Type material. Holotype (♀): ‘Vietnam / Kon Tum prov., Dak Ung / 05/2025 / local collector leg.’, (CPV).

The type is provided with a printed red label: ‘*Paranaspia mimula* sp. nov. / HOLOTYPUS / P. Viktora det., 2025’.

Description. Habitus of female holotype as in Fig. 7. Body largely ochre yellow, elongate, relatively robust, punctate, with setation. Body length from head to elytral apex 12.65 mm, widest at two thirds of elytral length from base to apex (4.50 mm), 2.81 times as long as wide.

Head ochre yellow, glossy, widest across eyes, distinctly narrower than pronotum at base, strongly strangled near base, microwrinkled, largely with irregular, shallow, sparse punctation/granulation. Disc and frons with narrow longitudinal furrow. Head with long, sparse, yellowish setation (longest in anterior part and on antennal insertions). Anterior part of head significantly prolonged anteriorly. Interspace between antennal insertions narrow, antennal insertions elevated on inner side. Eyes large, convex, blackish, small-faceted, slightly emarginate on inner side. Clypeus and labrum glossy, ochre yellow/pale brown, partly with yellowish setae. Mandibles ochre yellow with narrowly blackish tip, glossy, with sparse micropunctation and indistinct yellowish setation in margins.

Maxillary palpi ochre yellow (last palpomere partly darkly brown), glossy. Palpomeres widened apically (last palpomere grain-shaped with narrowed apex), microwrinkled, covered by indistinct, sparse, short, yellowish setation.

Antennae with 11 antennomeres, narrow, filiform, antennomeres slightly widened apically. Antennae long, reaching apical margin of elytra (Fig. 7). Antennomeres blackish (scape largely pale reddish-brown). Antennomeres 1–4 semi-glossy, antennomeres 5–11 matte. Antennomeres with dense, small-sized, shallow punctation/granulation, covered by dark setation, antennomeres 1–4 with longer, yellowish setation on inner side. Antennomeres without spines, some antennomeres slightly curved. Antennomere 2 shortest, antennomere 11 longest. Ratios of relative lengths of antennomeres 1–11 equal to: 0.93 : 0.24 : 1.00 : 0.77 : 1.14 : 1.26 : 1.23 : 1.22 : 1.17 : 0.89 : 1.34.

Pronotum transverse, ochre yellow, glossy, distinctly convex, only slightly narrower than elytra at humeri, strangled near anterior margin, slightly strangled near basal margin, widest at base, narrowest at anterior margin, lateral margins slightly undulate, anterior margin almost straight, base undulate (shape of pronotum as in Fig. 7). Pronotum 1.56 times as wide as long at base (widest point of pronotum) and 1.53 times as long as wide at anterior margin (narrowest point of pronotum). Pronotal disc smooth, glossy, with visible, irregular punctation mainly in lateral margins and basal angles, with very sparse, long, erect yellowish setae (denser and more visible in lateral margins and basal angles).

Scutellum ochre yellow, glossy, triangular with acute tip, microwrinkled, with very sparse, indistinct, yellowish setation.

Elytra slightly elongate, almost parallel, widest at two thirds of elytral length from base to apex, 8.85 mm long and 4.50 mm wide (1.96 times as long as wide), ochre yellow, glossy. Elytral disc slightly convex, microwrinkled, with sparse, relatively large-sized punctation (coarser and more distinct in basal two thirds of elytra), covered by sparse, regular yellowish setation, apical margin with denser setation with admixture of darker setae. Elytral apex cut, slightly undulate, rounded at basal angles, sutural angles acute with distinct spines (Fig. 7).

Pygidium ochre yellow, glossy, microwrinkled, with sparse, irregular, shallow punctation, covered by sparse, short, yellowish setation. Apical margin rounded.

Legs long and narrow, largely semi-glossy, femora ochre yellow with darker apical margins, tibiae and tarsi black. Legs microwrinkled, with shallow, irregular punctation (punctures larger on tibiae), covered by goldenish and dark setation. Setation longest in apical parts of tibiae. Femora narrowly club-shaped, tibiae widened apically. Metatibiae and metafemora distinctly longer than pro- and mesotibiae and pro- and mesofemora. Tibial spurs pale

reddish-brown, narrow, sharp, indistinctly curved. Tarsi long and narrow, microwrinkled, with shallow, irregular, large-sized punctation, covered by long, dark and goldenish setation. Metatarsomere 1 1.80 times longer than metatarsomeres 2 and 3 combined.

Ventral side of body ochre yellow (metepisternum and metasternum partly darkly brown), glossy, with small-sized punctation, partly covered by goldenish pubescence and setation (most dense on metepisternum and metasternum), ventrites almost completely covered by relatively sparse goldenish pubescence. Elytral epipleura narrow, ochre yellow, microwrinkled, with one line of small-sized punctures.

Male. Unknown.

Differential diagnosis. The most similar species are *Paranaspia frainii* (Fairmaire, 1897) (Fig. 8), described from India (Sikkim), and *Paranaspia reductipennis* (Pic, 1928) (Fig. 9), described from China (Yunnan).

Paranaspia mimula **sp. nov.** differs from the similar species *P. frainii* and *P. reductipennis* by more robust and less elongate body, unicolored (ochre yellow) head and scutellum (head and scutellum darker in *P. frainii* and *P. reductipennis*), paler femora, pronotum of distinctly different shape, unicolored elytra (with larger or smaller dark part in apical part of elytra in *P. frainii* and *P. reductipennis*), and by different shape of elytral apical margin with lateral angles prolonged into distinct spines in *Paranaspia mimula* **sp. nov.** (Figs. 7–9).

Etymology. From Latin *mimula* (meaning: “actress”).

Distribution. Vietnam (Kon Tum).

Genus *Leptostrangalia* Nakane & K. Ohbayashi, 1959

Type species. *Strangalia hosohana* Ohbayashi, 1952.

Leptostrangalia marketae **sp. nov.**

<https://zoobank.org/CDE2BA39-77B5-49F0-9414-8F47EE6B6664>

Fig. 10

Type locality. Vietnam, Dak Lak Province.

Type material. Holotype (♂): ‘Vietnam / Dak Lak / 6/2025 / local collector leg.’, (CPV).

The type is provided with a printed red label: ‘*Leptostrangalia marketae* sp. nov. / HOLOTYPUS / P. Viktora det., 2025’.

Description. Habitus of male holotype as in Fig. 10a. Body from pale yellowish to black, elongate, narrow, almost parallel, punctate, with pubescence. Body length from head to elytral apex 12.30 mm, widest at humeral part of elytra (2.75 mm), 4.47 times as long as wide.

Head black, widest across eyes, slightly narrower than pronotum at base, strongly strangled near base, largely with irregular, dense punctation, partly with dense punctation/granulation (mainly in frons), semi-glossy. Disc and frons with narrow longitudinal furrow. Head covered by recumbent, goldenish pubescence, partly with very long, erect, yellowish setae (mainly at anterior part). Head prolonged anteriorly. Interspace between antennal insertions very narrow, antennal insertions elevated into thorns on inner side. Eyes distinct, large, convex, goldenish, small-faceted, only slightly emarginate on inner side. Clypeus and labrum glossy, ochre yellow, partly with yellowish setae. Mandibles from ochre yellow to black tip, glossy, with pale setation in margins.

Maxillary palpi blackish brown, glossy. Palpomeres with narrowly pale yellowish apex, cylindrical, widened apically (last palpomere grain-shaped with narrowed apex), microwrinkled, covered by indistinct, sparse, short, yellowish setation.

Antennae with 11 antennomeres, narrow, elongate, filiform, antennomeres slightly widened apically (antennomere 11 slightly curved, narrowed apically into tip). Antennae long, exceeding apical margin of elytra (Fig. 10a). Antennomeres 1–4 blackish brown, antennomere 5 largely ochre yellow with partly darker margins and narrowly darker apex, antennomeres 6–7 largely ochre yellow with narrowly darker apex, antennomeres 8–11

largely blackish brown (irregularly covered by small areas of ochre yellow colour). Antennomeres 1–4 semi-glossy, antennomeres 5–11 semi-matte. Antennae with dense, small-sized punctation, covered by yellowish pubescence, antennomeres with longer yellowish setation on inner side (mainly in apical parts). Antennomeres with rounded apex, without spines, some antennomeres slightly curved. Antennomere 2 shortest, antennomere 5 longest. Ratios of relative lengths of antennomeres 1–11 equal to: 0.85 : 0.16 : 1.00 : 0.85 : 1.38 : 1.37 : 1.36 : 1.32 : 1.21 : 1.11 : 1.35.

Pronotum elongate, black, semi-glossy, convex, narrower than elytra at humeri, strangled near anterior margin, slightly strangled near basal margin, widest at base, narrowest at anterior margin, lateral margins slightly undulate, anterior margin almost straight, base undulate (shape of pronotum as in Fig. 10a). Pronotum 1.04 times as long as wide at base (widest point of pronotum) and 1.95 times as long as wide at anterior margin. Pronotal disc completely with very dense, small-sized granulate punctation, covered by relatively sparse, goldenish pubescence (longer in basal angles and anterior margin of pronotum), basal part with a few long, erect, colourless setae.

Scutellum black, elongated, shield-shaped, microwrinkled, semi-glossy, with sparse, recumbent, yellowish pubescence.

Elytra elongate, narrow, narrowing apically, 7.57 mm long and 2.75 mm wide (2.75 times as long as wide), black with pale yellowish spots/stripes (Fig. 10a), semi-glossy. Elytral disc relatively flat, microwrinkled, completely with dense, small-sized punctation, covered by yellowish and blackish pubescence with lustre (distinctly denser at apical half of elytra), apical margin with long yellowish setation. Elytral apex cut, apical margin slightly undulate, lateral angles with short spine (Fig. 10a).

Pygidium brown with ochre yellow apical part, glossy in apical part, microwrinkled, with shallow, small-sized punctation, covered by relatively sparse yellowish pubescence and setation. Apical angles rounded.

Legs very long and narrow, largely black, semi-glossy, microwrinkled, with dense, small-sized punctation, largely covered by yellowish pubescence and setation (setation longest in apical parts of tibiae). Femora narrowly club-shaped, tibiae widened apically. Metatibiae and metafemora distinctly longer than pro- and mesotibiae and pro- and mesofemora. Tibial spurs reddish-brown, narrow, sharp, slightly curved. Tarsi long and narrow (metatarsi extremely long), blackish brown, microwrinkled, with small-sized punctation, covered by long, yellowish setation. Claws large and distinct. Metatarsomere 1 1.50 times longer than metatarsomeres 2 and 3 combined.

Ventral side of body largely black (partly with small ochre yellow spots/stripes mainly on coxae and sparsely in margins of ventrites), glossy, with very dense, small-sized punctation, largely covered by dense, recumbent, goldenish pubescence. Elytral epipleura narrow, black, glossy, with micropunctation and sparse pale setation.

Genitalia as in Fig. 10b.

Female. Unknown.

Differential diagnosis. The most similar species are *Leptostrangalia trisignatipennis* Hayashi, 1979, described from Malaysia (Pahang), and *Leptostrangalia celebiana* N. Ohbayashi, 2019, described from Indonesia (South Sulawesi).

Leptostrangalia marketae **sp. nov.** differs from the similar species *L. trisignatipennis* and *L. celebiana* by wider and less elongate pronotum, darker antennae and profemora, distinctly longer metatarsi, and by less elongate elytra with distinctly different pattern of dark and pale spots/stripes.

Leptostrangalia marketae **sp. nov.** has similar pattern of dark and pale spots/stripes on elytra to *Davidiela haucki* (Holzschuh, 2011), from which it differs, however, by significantly longer metatarsi and filiform antennomeres (distinctly serrate in *Davidiela haucki*).

Etymology. The species is dedicated to my wife Markéta.

Distribution. Vietnam (Dak Lak).

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